

This document contains the semi-structured interview script for the paper “*Understanding the Functions of the Review Process in the Era of Agentic Development*”. The semi-structured interview was conducted online and recorded. It has four sections plus introduction and wrap-up. For the interviews, participants were offered a choice of one of the following incentives: a USD 100 gift card, a one-year subscription to **Company Name¹** products, or a USD 100 donation to a charity of their choice.

Introduction (5 minutes)

[greetings]

[check if the connection is ok]

My name is ___, and I am a researcher at [organization name], [introduce others presented]

First of all, I would like to thank you for your willingness to join our research. Just to make it clear, we are trying to learn how the involvement of AI reshape the functions of code review.

Have you ever participated in user studies/ interviews before?

Then you know that there are no right or wrong answers in such sessions. We are really interested in your way of work and your personal experience.

Our interview will last approximately 1 hour. Also, it will be recorded, but we keep all recordings confidential. We will make anonymized summaries out of them, and once the research is over, we will delete recordings and all personal data that we gathered.

Do you have any questions? [discuss questions]

Now let me start the recording, and when it starts, I will ask for your permission to record this session one more time.

[start recording]

I would like to have your permission to record this session [get the permission]

Just to get started...

Tell us about your current role. How many people are on your team?

¹ Name hidden for double-blind review purposes. This company is an international IT company specializing in software development.

AI Setup (15 minute)

Which project are you working on? In which domain?

What is your current setup?

How often do you use agentic AI tools in your development workflow?

Which type of AI coding and development assistance do you use at work?

- Agents operating on your machine in (plugins for) code editors (*the agent generates and/or edits files*)
- Agents operating on your machine via CLI or terminal (*the agent generates and/or edits files*)
- Agents operating in cloud environments (e.g. operating on GitHub, GitLab)

Core Block (35 minutes)

Anchor

Now I would like to focus on a specific recent example.

Can you walk me through the last time you developed a feature? Could you briefly describe your pipeline?

Eliciting Process Functions

[If the review step is there] → What is the main purpose of review in the described pipeline?

When you're reviewing something, what do you pay the most attention to?

What do you pay attention to when reviewing PR from your colleague?

What do you pay attention to when you review output from your agent?

You've already shared the purpose of the review for the particular case. Could you please recall cases where the review's purpose was different?

Before AI & What Changed

Thank you, it was very interesting to learn how you do it now. And now I would like you to think back on the time when you did not use AI tools. Please, can you briefly share how you were developing code before AI?

And how were you reviewing?

Do you think that the review purpose has generally changed now? Or, if it used to have a few purposes, can we now say that at least something has changed? And what exactly changed, if yes?

Why do you think this has changed? Is there something that became more/less important from your pov?

Is this [function] no longer important at all when you develop code?

Is it still part of the review?

[Optional] For each purpose, please rate how important it is in your current work? Please use a scale from 1 (not important at all) to 5 (very important). For each purpose, please rate how important it was, if you recall your work before using AI tools? Please use a scale from 1 (not important at all) to 5 (very important).

Review Load & Coping

Let's get back to the present.

Do you feel that the amount of review work increased? What is the most difficult?

What helps you to deal with that overload?

New Review Objects & Validation

[If it was not mentioned before] Is there anything new that you review now apart from PRs? If yes, could you describe how the review conducted in such cases?

If there is a specification / something mentioned: What do you pay attention to when reviewing [artifact name]?

How do you validate output vs. input? What are the differences?

How would you call this type of work, when you validate a specification / something that you mentioned?

Depth Probes

[Depending on the deepness of the answers and whether additional information is needed, possible follow-ups]:

What happens if you skip the review step?

What are the signs that review is done sufficiently? How do you check them?

[Goal: we try to extract functions, not actions]

[Next, the goal is to understand whether some functions have become less important overall, or whether they are now handled elsewhere in the process.]

Do you use agents to review your own proposals?

Knowledge Transfer (10 min)

Everyday we learn something new. Now I'd like to talk about how you learn or how you help your colleagues.

Could you please recall a case when review was a kind of education for you? What have you learned?

[Depending on the answer]:

- When your colleague does not understand something during the review process, what did you do last time?
- When you don't understand something during the review process, what did you do last time?

Has this changed since you started using AI in the review process?

Do you ask colleagues more or less often than before?

Do you feel that you learn while writing code with agents?

Wrap-Up (5 minutes)

Is there anything we didn't ask that you think is important?

Do you have any questions?

Many thanks for your participation in the study, we greatly appreciate it!

Please let us know which reward you would like to receive as a thank you for your participation:

- a USD 100 gift card
- a one-year subscription to *Company Name*¹ products
- a USD 100 charity donation